

Sample 33a

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0010
	{Si}	74.8
	{Al, Si}	6.9
	{Fe}	4.7
	{Al, Si, K}	4.0
	{Al}	1.3
	{Si, K}	0.9
	{Mg, Si}	0.8
	{Ti}	0.7
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.6
	{Si, Fe}	0.6
	{Na, Al, Si}	0.6
	{Si, Ca LoP}	0.6
	{Ca}	0.5
	{Si, Fe}	0.4
	{P, Ca}	0.4
	{Si, Ca HIP}	0.3
	{Na, Si}	0.3
	{Na, Si, Cl}	0.2
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.2
	{Al, Ca}	0.1
	{Cl}	0.1
	{Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Si, P}	0.1
	{P, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.1
	{Cl}	0.1
	{S, Ba-LA1}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{Si, Cl}	0.1
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{Al, Si, Ti}	0.0
	{Al, Fe}	0.0
	{Mg, Fe}	0.0
	{S}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.0
Pellet	0.0
Ore preparation undifferentiated	0.1
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.1
BOF converter slag	0.0
BOF converter slag slopping	0.6
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.0
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Olivine flux	0.3
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.1
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.1
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	34.3
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	2.6
Carbon rich - other	6.8
Cement or BOF converter	0.0
Cement	0.2
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.3
Ba-sulphate bearing	1.7
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	49.6
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	2.8
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.4
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.0

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	0.1
Site - ore / hot metal	0.1
Site - slag	0.6
Site - slag; urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.3
Site - flux / slag; + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.1
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.1
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	34.3
Site - carbon-rich other	2.6
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	6.8
Urban; rarely site - slag	0.0
Urban	2.2
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	49.6
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	2.8
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.4
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.0

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 33b

Greyscale Image

143 μm

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0104
	{Si}	66.1
	{Al, Si}	9.1
	{Fe}	5.4
	{Na, Al, Si}	4.5
	{Mg, Si}	3.5
	{Al, Si, K}	1.9
	{Na, Si}	1.3
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.3
	{Al}	1.0
	{Ti}	0.6
	{Si, Fe}	0.6
	{Ca}	0.5
	{Si, Ca LoP}	0.5
	{S, Ca}	0.4
	{Si, Fe}	0.4
	{Si, K}	0.4
	{S}	0.3
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.3
	{Ca, Fe}	0.3
	{Si, Ca HIP}	0.3
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.1
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{S, Fe}	0.1
	{Cl}	0.1
	{S, Ba-LA1}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{P, Ca}	0.1
	{Si, Cl}	0.1
	{Al, Ca}	0.1
	{Al, Si, Ti}	0.1
	{Mg, P}	0.0
	{Mg}	0.0
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.0
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.3
Pellet	0.1
Ore preparation undifferentiated	1.1
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.2
BOF converter slag	0.0
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.0
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Olivine flux	2.5
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.1
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	31.2
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	2.6
Carbon rich - other	4.9
Cement or BOF converter	0.0
Cement	0.2
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	4.2
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	49.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	3.6
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.0

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	1.5
Site - ore / hot metal	0.2
Site - slag	0.0
Site - slag; urban	0.0
Site - flux	2.5
Site - flux / slag; + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.0
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.1
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	31.2
Site - carbon-rich other	2.6
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	4.9
Urban; rarely site - slag	0.0
Urban	4.4
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	49.0
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	3.6
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.0

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 33c

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0042
	{Si}	75.1
	{Al, Si}	9.0
	{Fe}	5.4
	{Al, Si, K}	1.7
	{Al}	1.7
	{Na, Al, Si}	1.0
	{Mg, Si}	0.8
	{Si, Fe}	0.7
	{Na, Si}	0.6
	{Si, Ca LoP}	0.5
	{Si, K}	0.3
	{Ca}	0.3
	{Mg}	0.3
	{Ti}	0.3
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.3
	{Si, Ca HIP}	0.3
	{Si, Fe}	0.2
	{Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{Zn-LA1}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.1
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.1
	{P, Ca}	0.1
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{S, Ba-LA1}	0.1
	{Al, Ca}	0.1
	{K}	0.0
	{Na, Si, Cl}	0.0
	{Cl}	0.0
	{S}	0.0
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.0
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.0
	{Mg, Si, Fe}	0.0
	{Al, Si, Ti}	0.0
	{P}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.3
Pellet	0.1
Ore preparation undifferentiated	1.6
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.2
BOF converter slag	0.0
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.0
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Olivine flux	0.2
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.3
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.2
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	31.4
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	1.0
Carbon rich - other	4.1
Cement or BOF converter	0.0
Cement	1.1
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	1.2
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.6
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	55.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	2.2
Misc silicates including natural	0.4
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.0

141 μm

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	2.1
Site - ore / hot metal	0.2
Site - slag	0.0
Site - slag; urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.2
Site - flux / slag; + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.0
Site - flux / refractory	0.3
Site - refractory	0.2
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	31.4
Site - carbon-rich other	1.0
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	4.1
Urban; rarely site - slag	0.0
Urban	2.9
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	55.0
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	2.2
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.4
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.0

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels